

From Curriculum to Classroom: Teachers' Institutional Knowledge in Developing Pupils' Reading Competences through Internal Didactic Transposition

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Abstract: Teachers use internal didactic transposition to facilitate the movement from “knowledge to be taught” (curriculum) to “taught knowledge” and “learned knowledge”. However, the impact of this movement is poorly analysed in the literature, and the role played by teachers and their approaches is poorly studied. This study investigated how internal didactic transposition takes place in the pedagogical discourse of primary school teachers; studied the impact of this transposition on the development of pupils’ reading competences; and the role played by the teacher relationship to institutional knowledge in this transposition. Through qualitative ethnographic participant research method guided by the constructivist paradigm, the study finds that primary school teachers’ institutional relationship to reading bodies of knowledge is flawed and negatively affects the development of pupils reading competences. Effective transposition of knowledge from curriculum to classroom significantly enhances pupils’ reading skills and contributes to quality education. In all, the study underscores the critical role of teachers’ engagement with institutional knowledge in providing quality education and developing learners’ reading competencies. Future studies suggest to policy makers to rethink about Professional Development and Monitoring, granting teachers access to Institutional Documents, provide Specialized Training on Basic Knowledge and organize regular In-School Seminars and Follow-Up.

Keywords: Didactics, Didactic Transposition/ Internal Didactic Transposition, Relationship to Knowledge, Reading, Reading Competence.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The question of knowledge cannot be separated from didactics and didactic transposition mindful of didactics preoccupation of knowledge as an object of teaching and learning, constituting formerly depersonalized bodies of knowledge of a discipline (Reutel et al, 2013). The Didactic Transposition concept said to be introduced in the field of didactics by Chevallard in 1985, (Bosch & Gascon, 2006; Chevallard & Bosch, 2013) “refers to the transformation a body of knowledge undergoes from the moment it is produced, put to use, selected and designed to be taught, until

it is actually taught in a given educational institution” (Chevallard & Bosch, 2013). To Chevallard, processing knowledge within the teaching system is the main didactic problem (Chevallard, 1989, p. 5). The notion didactic transposition postulated in several literature, is precisely to describe and explain the phenomena of transformation of knowledge from its production up to its teaching (Bosch & Gascón, 2006, Chevallard, 2007; 2019; 2020; Chevallard & Bosch, 2020, Stromskag & Chevallard, 2024). The schematic presentation below illustrates Chevallards didactic transposition process:

Fig 1: The Didactic Transposition Process Illustrated by Yves Chevallard
 Source: Chevallard, (1985; 1991; Ravel, 2003; Bosch & Garçon, 2006)

The schema above divides the process into two principal stages; the passage from “scholarly knowledge to Knowledge to be taught” (external didactic transposition), and the passage from “knowledge to be taught to learned knowledge” (internal didactic transposition) (Chevallard, 1985, 1991; 2015; Ravel, 2003; Bosch & Garçon, 2006; Chevallard & Bosch, 2013).

Our study focuses on the “internal didactic transposition” which involves the movement from “knowledge to be taught” to “taught knowledge” and “learned knowledge”. In other words, it concerns the transition of knowledge from curriculum to classroom (Ravel, 2003; Bosch & Gascon, 2006). The role of the teacher according to Ravel, (2003) is central in the internal didactic transposition process (Ravel, 2003, p. 4). A significant change occurs when knowledge is integrated into the teaching system due to specific laws and constraints unique to the didactic relation (Chevallard, 1989; Ravel, 2003). Teachers are not free to choose the knowledge they wish to teach at any level; they must adhere to the noospherian choices outlined in the curriculum (termed by Chevallard as ‘knowledge to be taught’) (Chevallard, 1989, Ravel, 2003). Ravel (2003) identifies an intermediary step termed ‘prepared knowledge’ involved in transposing knowledge from curriculum (Ravel 2003). This intermediate stage includes breaking down curriculum knowledge to create a scheme of work, from which individual lesson plans (taught knowledge) are prepared. The goal is to develop the competences expected by society in learners. Empirical examples (Chevallard 1989; 1991; 2015; Ravel, 2003; Bosch & Garçon, 2006) illustrate the complexities of the relation and procession of knowledge. Observing different classrooms often reveals discrepancies in how the same lesson is delivered by different teachers,

prompting questions about the consistency of knowledge transfer from curriculum to classroom practice (Ravel 2003). The task therefore, of Didactic Transposition, as described by Chevallard, involves transformation of bodies of knowledge into teachable content (Chevallard, 1989; Chevallard & Bosch, 2013). As Bosch & Garçon present; “There exist a process, a social construction with multiple actors and different temporalities, through which some of these bodies of knowledge have to be selected, delimited, reorganized, and redefined until reaching the classroom (Bosch & Gascon, 2006, p. 55). This transformation is essential for establishing knowledge as teachable (Chevallard, 1989). Chevallard’s concept of didactic transposition in Mathematics has been adapted to the didactics of English/Reading at the internal level in this study.

English is a fundamental school subject in Cameroon and it cuts across other subject areas. The Cameroon primary curriculum classifies it under ‘Basic Knowledge’ as it is essential for literacy, numeracy, and 21st-century competencies. It covers the listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills necessary for national and international communication (Aka Mba, 2017; MINEDUB- Cameroon Primary School Curriculum, 2018/19). English is compulsory from pre-primary to tertiary levels, preparing pupils for effective use in various domains such as research, trade, and communication (NSESPPS, 2000, Nforbi, 2013, CPSC, 2018/19). Reading being a crucial language skill which as well cuts across subject areas is emphasized to be fundamental for any educational system (MINEDUB-2018/19). Apart from just being a core competency recognized to contribute to lifelong learning and sustainable development (ADEA, 2012), Reading is a fundamental human right, basic human need for citizens of every nation

and primary goal of formal education (UNESCO, -UDHR, 1948; EFA- Jomtien, 1990; Dakar, 2000; Rep. of Cameroon, 1998, MINEDUB, 2022) The curriculum further explains that Reading helps in developing intellectual, cultural, emotional, spiritual, and economic skills. The aim of Reading according to the Cameroon primary curriculum is for pupils to read and understand documents, continue their education, and integrate into society (MINEDUB, 2018/19).

Despite its indispensable importance, reading outcome of Pupils in Cameroon's primary school have often fall short of curriculum expectations (Nalova, 2016; Akah Mba, 2017; CPSC, 2018/19). We assume that that teachers' flawed institutional relationship to EL/Reading bodies of knowledge impacts the development of pupils Reading competencies. This means teachers' inability to effectively transpose reading bodies of knowledge from the curriculum to classroom seriously impact the development of pupils reading skills. This is due to the fact that teachers do not take cognizance of the vital role effective transposition play in building learners competences. This defect highlights the need for enhanced methods and techniques to develop communication competences, emphasizing on the reading and writing skills so as to meet curriculum outcomes and support lifelong learning and sustained development. Thus, the question of quality of the teacher through their relationship to institutional knowledge. UNESCO's Director General Irena Bokova links the quality of education system to the quality of teacher (EFA-Global Monitoring Report, 2014), emphasizes that "poor –quality education is a significant barrier to learning", giving that many children graduate from primary school without acquiring basic learning skills (EFA- Global Monitoring Report, 2014). Education is the priority to the Cameroonian nation, and the teacher is designated as a main guarantor of quality (Law N° 98/004, 1998).

Despite efforts to achieve universal literacy and quality education in Cameroon (...), there still remain a slow growth in pupils reading proficiency, as many pupils graduate from primary school without acquiring basic reading skills (Nalova, 2016, Akah Mba, 2017; CPSC, 2018/19). Stating the general purpose of education, The Law of Orientation of Education in Cameroon, (Law N°98/004, 1998) underscores the necessity 'to train children for their intellectual development and their harmonious societal integration'. Studies have however found flaws in teachers' ability in teaching Reading, highlighting issues related to lesson planning, classroom management and evaluation (Nalova, 2016; Akah Mba, 2017, MINEDUB, 2018/19...). To meet educational goals and enhance learners' competencies in Reading, teachers' relationship to knowledge needs to be addressed, with emphases on good mastery of subject and good pedagogic skills. This means in other words that Quality internal didactic transposition, facilitated by teachers' relationship to institutional knowledge, is crucial for ensuring quality education. It thus involves effective transformation of curriculum knowledge to classroom knowledge. The focus of this study in investigating teachers' institutional relationship to English/Reading bodies of knowledge through internal didactic transposition aims to observe and interpret teachers'

understanding of their institutional responsibilities and how it influence pupils Reading competences. The researcher of the study therefore participated in natural setting to gain insight into the effectiveness of the transposition process in building reading skills.

➤ *General Research Question*

- In what ways does the teachers' relationship to institutional knowledge influence the development of pupils' reading competence?

The general objective is oriented towards institutional norms/ responsibilities of teachers, side by side classroom practices.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study focused on examining teachers' institutional relationship to knowledge through internal didactic transposition of reading bodies of knowledge (from curriculum to classroom). The study adopted a qualitative methodological approach grounded in the interpretivist (naturalistic) paradigm sometimes referred to as constructivist paradigm (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005; Cresswell, 2007). This approach seeks to understand the subjective experiences of participants by studying phenomena in their natural environments and interpreting findings based on the researchers' own experiences and backgrounds. The present study asserts that proper internal didactic transposition of English / Reading through teachers' relationship to institutional knowledge impacts learners' reading competencies. Consequently, the researcher adopts an ethnographic research strategy to gain an insider view of this process in Cameroon primary schools. Therefore the researcher employs multiple methods of inquiry required for ethnographic research, including participant observation, studying institutional and classroom documents, observing teachers' classroom activities, conducting semi-structured in-depth interviews, administering reading tests to pupils, and taking field notes from informal discussions. This approach allows the researcher to immerse in the schools as both a participant and an observer (Ritchie & Lewis, 2003; Denzin & Lincoln, 2005; Atkinson & Hammersley, 2007; Amin, 2005; Mukheji & Albon, 2010; Gray, 2014). The population includes primary school teachers and pupils in Yaoundé – Mfoundi Division, focusing on their roles in transforming "knowledge to be taught" into "taught knowledge" to facilitate learning. Using documents from the Delegation of Education in charge of Mfoundi Division and the Inspectorate of Education in charge of Yaounde VI, 12 Government primary schools with a total of 4609 pupils and 177 qualified teachers of Yaounde VI were targeted. However, we purposefully selected 10 class 5 and class 6 teachers with 689 pupils of three government primary schools of Yaounde VI. This is because of our assumption that as a final level in the primary cycle, class 5 and 6 pupils are assumed to have acquired basic reading skills. This focus allows for a detailed immersive observation of the didactic transposition process. Key considerations included sample size, schedule feasibility, and socio-demographic characteristics of teachers

(Cohen et al., 2007; Burgess, 1982a/1984; Ritchie et al., 2010). The sample frame was guided by institutional records from the inspectorate of education and the head offices of government schools in Yaoundé VI. These records included forms for teachers' effective presence and general school timetables, ensuring comprehensive demographic information and confirming the selection of class 5 and 6 teachers. This approach helped manage the sample size while ensuring depth in data collection.

A. Participant Observation

Participant observation is a key aspect of ethnographic research, which involves studying people in their everyday lives to understand their social worlds through thick descriptions and interpretations. Cresswell (2007) emphasizes that extended observation through participant observation involves researchers immersing in people's daily lives, observing, interviewing, and recording activities to gain firsthand insights into their habits, beliefs, and language. This method is crucial for collecting firsthand data on teachers' relationships to knowledge of EL/Reading through didactic transposition. In this study, the researcher used participant observation to interact with teachers and pupils, observe classroom activities, analyze institutional documents, collect field notes, and conduct semi-structured interviews.

B. Interview

Giving the necessity of ethical considerations in ethnographic research, this study's researcher plays a balanced role of observer-as-participant (observed teachers' documents and classroom activities, making critical notes) and participant-as-observer (taught lessons and tested students' reading abilities), with both teachers and pupils aware of the research and its purpose. The approach included field notes, informal discussions, and semi-structured interviews, and maintained a balance between observing and participating, ensuring ethical considerations were met. The interviews which lasted between 26 and 40 minutes, were conducted to capture participants' perceptions of the didactic transposition of EL/Reading in primary schools. It focused on the research questions and objectives. Ethical principles such as informed consent, confidentiality, and protection from harm were strictly followed.

C. Document Study

Documentary research complemented the observations, interviews, tests, and informal discussions. It enabled the study of institutional documents to answer research questions and verify teachers' claims. Key documents studied included:

- **Curriculum:** represents Knowledge to be taught and Guides competence development and teaching strategies.
- **Mise en Place des Effectifs des Enseignants:** Provides demographic data of teachers.
- **Scheme of Work Book:** Chronological plans for subjects.
- **Lesson Notes Book:** Weekly and daily lesson plans.
- **Class Timetable:** Comparison of allocated and actual teaching time.
- **Record of Work Book:** Documents daily and weekly lessons taught.

- **Pupils' Books:** Compared with other documents to check lesson correspondence.
- **Class Register:** Data on pupils' attendance, gender, and ages.

D. Informal Discussion

Informal discussions were used to fill in gaps from observations, interviews, and document studies. Data were recorded in a notebook whenever the researcher received new information or needed clarification.

E. Ability Test

The ability test diagnosed pupils' reading competences in terms of fluency and comprehension. It validated researcher's assumptions and study's motivation, assessing pupils' ability to read, understand, and comprehend texts. Two tests with the same content were administered in two intervals; one without any lesson and the other after a 45-minutes lesson on health. The test included oral, written, and practical components to develop reading fluency and positive attitudes towards reading. The curriculum recommends this holistic evaluation approach to ensure comprehensive competence development. The test were administered to pupils with due permission from the school administration and parents, meeting ethical norms.

F. Procedure of Data Collection

The researcher started the data collection process by securing authorization from the Faculty of Education. This was essential for negotiating access to the research setting. Ethical guidelines were followed to ensure research integrity. The researcher was granted permission from the Inspectorate of Basic Education Yaoundé VI, to collect data in selected schools after piloting her tools. Demographic data were then collected from the Inspectorate and individual schools.

G. Method of Data Analyses

Analyzing qualitative data began with cleaning the data to ensure it was error-free. The researcher then reviewed the original research objectives and questions to ensure alignment with the study's goals. Familiarization with the data involved watching observation videos, reading notes, arranging institutional documents, and comparing interviews with field notes, providing a general overview before detailed analysis. The researcher used both Textual and Thematic analysis methods. Textual analysis explored layers of meaning within observation and interview data, focusing on language, context, and structure. Thematic analysis identified patterns, themes, and meanings within the data, using an inductive approach. The researcher used the SONAL software platform for transcription, breaking down interviews into manageable chunks, facilitating coding and categorization. Through these processes, the researcher ensured a comprehensive and detailed analysis of the collected data, aligning the findings with the research questions and objectives.

III. FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

The main research task of this study was to examine teachers' institutional relationship to knowledge from the backdrop of internal didactic transposition. This permits us to verify how this transposition process helps in the development of pupils' reading competences. The guided research question asking what ways the teachers' institutional relationship to knowledge influence the development of pupils' reading competences was handled and analysed within the concept of didactic transposition, didactic triangle and epistemological obstacle. Given that a teacher cannot be analyzed as an isolated entity but rather as an institutional subject under the institution of school, constraint by the general goals of education in particular societies, Institutional relationship to knowledge within the context of the present study requires **teachers' knowledge or perception of their role / responsibilities as institutional objects, and their relationship to knowledge of institutional documents (availability, use, and perceptions)**. Findings related to this part are retrieved analyzed data from Observed institutional documents, interview from participant teachers, and informal discussion.

A. Teachers' Knowledge/Perception on their Role and Responsibility

➤ Data from Interview

Interview data related to institutional Relationship to knowledge came from two main and prompt questions; what are your responsibilities as a primary school teacher? and how do you plan your lessons and what documents of reference do you actually use in planning?

➤ INT: as a Teacher, what are Some of your Responsibilities as Prescribed by the Ministry of Basic Education?

- Teaching pupils, - good morals, (5teachers)
- Brining up intellectually (2 teachers)
- Make sure the children fit well in the society, be good citizens (2teachers)
- Make children know to read and write and also to add figures... (1 teacher).
- Write lessons, have all the necessary documents (1teacher),
- Give notes to pupils, (1 teacher)
- To **evaluate** and **grade** pupils (1teacher)
- Help pupils **attain the objectives** (1teacher)

Some related literature describe Teachers as all persons responsible for the (Quality) education of pupils. To some others however, the teacher's role is to a great extent determined by the nature of the objectives which his/her society assigns to the school since it is the only agency concerned with formal education; and in the formalized institution of school, the community decides the particular kinds of skills and knowledge that needs to be maintained.

The teachers' perception or knowledge of their responsibilities matches a little with the recommendations of the 1998 law of Education orientation, which stipulates that

the teacher shall be the principal guarantor of the quality of education... and shall be bound to **teach, educate, provide educational guardians, promote the quest for scientific knowledge, carry out assessment, and be of moral rectitude.**

The teachers to some extent have some general understanding of their institutional responsibilities. However, some major aspects of their responsibilities such as the mediator, facilitator and knowledge organizer role were not mentioned by any of the teachers.

In addition to being analysed as an institutional subject who is constraint to institutional norms, the teacher construct and reconstruct praxiological organization of knowledge that represent what pupils have to learn. Therefore, teachers' relationship to institutional knowledge got much to do with their ability to identify and use some institutional documents as they play a great role in the realization of the didactic transposition process.

The data reveals that some of the teachers are aware of the necessity of institutional documents in organizing or planning lessons while other seem not to know. This is revealed in the excerpts below:

➤ INT: How do you plan your lesson and what document of reference do you actually use?

- Text book, curriculum, scheme,
- Curriculum according to my time table
- Teach sound and form words

Three teachers mentioned that they use the curriculum and other documents to plan their weekly lessons, yet when prompted to talk about the planning process, we notice that they do not actually understand the process. They provide the following summarized data:

➤ INT: So what procedure do you use in building your yearly to daily lesson plan?

- Start with sounds of alphabet, consonants, vowels and word formation
- Use the Reader, Dictionary and phone
- English text books, SWB books, and charts

The finding suggest a gross neglect of such an indispensable institutional didactic document. Meaning that the first stage of the internal didactic transposition process, is not recognized or respected and eventually not carried out by the teachers, thus, an uncordial relationship to institutional knowledge.

It can therefore be interpreted at this level that the teachers' have very little knowledge about necessity of these institutional classroom documents, thus, they fail to respect institutional norms. Their neglect of institutional responsibility might be because of lack of knowledge or mere disrespect of norms as later confirmed by finding of the observation and informal discussion data.

B. Teachers' Ownership and Use of Institutional Documents

➤ *Classroom observation – Document study Data*

• *The Curriculum*

Table 1: Individual Participants' Data Related to Ownership of a Copy of the Curriculum

Participant	Category of Situation	Indicator	Observation
S1BA5A1F	Owns a copy of curriculum	No	Does not own a copy of the curriculum nor the NSESPS (2000). Does not transpose knowledge from them
	Owns a copy of the NSESPS (2000)	No	
S1BA6A1F	Owns a copy of curriculum	No	Does not own a copy of the curriculum nor the NSESPS (2000). Does not transpose knowledge from them
S2BA5A2M	Owns a copy of the NSESPS (2000)	No	
	Owns a copy of curriculum	No	Does not own a copy of the curriculum nor the NSESPS (2000). Does not transpose knowledge from them
S2BA6A2F	Owns a copy of the NSESPS (2000)	No	
	Owns a copy of curriculum	No	Does not own a copy of the curriculum nor the NSESPS (2000). Does not transpose knowledge from them
S3E52AM	Owns a copy of the NSESPS (2000)	No	
	Owns a copy of curriculum	Yes	
S3E5A2F	Owns a copy of the NSESPS (2000)	No	Has never used NSESPS (2000)
	Owns a copy of curriculum	Yes	Owns a copy but does not transpose from it.
S3E6A2F	Owns a copy of curriculum	No	Does not own a copy of the curriculum nor the NSESPS (2000). Does not transpose knowledge from them
	Owns a copy of the NSESPS (2000)	No	
S3E6A2M	Owns a copy of curriculum	No	Does not own a copy of the curriculum nor the NSESPS (2000). Does not transpose knowledge from them
	Owns a copy of the NSESPS (2000)	No	

Source: Teachers' Individual Institutional Classroom Documents

• **Finding:** As shown on the table above, suggest that;

- ✓ **2 out of 8 participant** teachers (S3E52AM and S3E52AF) each have a copy of the New Primary School Curriculum but do not use them.
- ✓ **6 others out of 8, do not** have a copy of curriculum.

• *Data Informal Discussion*

The Informal discussion took place at different intervals between individual teachers and the researcher with the aim of finding out why teachers do not have copies of curriculum.

➤ *Seven teachers' responses analyzed and summarized thus:*

- The head teachers have the copies of the curriculum asked them to photo copy.
- Each of them have not yet done mostly because the contents are not explicitly organized.
- Others said they get it from the office each time they need to use it.

➤ *How the Two Teachers that have Copies of the Curriculum use them;*

- ✓ **S3BE5A2F** complained that the contents are mixed up and confusing, so she does not find it necessary using the curriculum.
- ✓ **S3BE5A2M** complained that the content does not match with the contents of the Reader, but when he finds anything useful from it he takes it to teach. The Reader has everything.

If we agree with Lenoire et al, (2002), that the teacher only plays a role in modifying or filtering the knowledge the learners already have following stated goals of the curriculum which stands as the voice of the society, then we would not be wrong to interpret that apart from being a show of disrespect to institutional norms, not having a copy of the curriculum also indicates that teachers do not play their role in transposing knowledge appropriately. This interpretation is due to the assumption according to the present study that Reading bodies of knowledge are not taken from the appropriate instituted source before bringing to the classroom. The teachers' attitudes towards institutional knowledge are observed to be negative. This can be confirmed from the findings of informal discussion and field notes data presented below.

➤ *The Scheme of Work Book*

The next group of tables below present data collected from the observation of the **Schemes of Work Book** of individual participating teachers with aim of finding out whether teachers actually have copies and how they use them.

The scheme of work is a didactically transposed knowledge by the teacher from *'knowledge to be taught'* to *'taught knowledge'*, marking the beginning of the Internal Didactic Transposition process.

Table 2: Individual Participants' Data Related to Ownership and Use of the Scheme of Work Book

Participant	Category of Situation	Indicator	Observation
S1BA5A1F	Owens a copy	Yes	Owens a scheme of work book but not using (Still planning to start using)
	Well transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	Yes	Within the six months of schooling, five projects were planned and three carried out
S1BA6A1F	Owens a copy	Yes	Teacher has an unused scheme of work book but still planning to start using
	Well transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	No	No project plan within six months of schooling.
S2BA5A2M	Owens a copy	Yes	Teacher has a scheme of work book but has not been using it. So no plans of work found in the book.
	Well transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	No	Within six months of schooling the teacher prepared and carryout only one project (filter) in February.
S2BA6A2F	Owens a copy	Yes	The teacher has not been using the book. No reason for not using the book.
	Transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	Yes	Within the six months of schooling, the teacher attempted to draw one incomplete project plan
	Category of Situation	Indicator	Observation
S3E52AM	Owens a copy	Yes	Has the book but has not been using. (ill health)
	Well transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	No	No project plan within six month of schooling
			Teacher owns a copy but has not been using. According to the teacher it is not necessary.
S3E5A2F	Owens a copy	Yes	No project within six months of schooling
	Well transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	No	
S3E6A2F	Owens a copy	Yes	Owens a scheme book but does not use it
	Well transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	No	No project plan within six months of schooling
S3E6A2M	Owens a copy	No	Does not own a scheme book and not using any.
	Well transposed monthly/yearly lesson plans in line with the Integrated Learning Themes?	No	
	Identified and Planned Projects for each Month?	No	No project plan within six months of schooling.

Source: Teachers' Individual Institutional Classroom Documents

➤ *The Above Data Reveals that:*

- **7 out of 8** teachers **have** scheme of work books. **1**teacher (**S3BE62BM**) **does not** have.

- **None of the scheme books have transposed lessons from the curriculum**
- Project plan (2 teachers - **S1BA5A2F** and **S2BA6A2F**) each drew few project plan but were not able to implement with the pupils.

For instance, teacher (S1BA5A1F) drew up five project plans, and was able to implement three. The projects include; sponges for bathing, flower beds, painting, toy boats and canoes, and first aid box.

➤ *Individual Lesson Note Book*

The next document observed was the **Individual Lesson Plan/Note Book presented on the tables below.** Considering a teacher as an institutional subject who has as

one of his responsibility to plan and teach lessons, the category of **lesson planning** is considered as a basic component of the **teachers’ institutional knowledge**. Each of the teachers have different ways of preparing, yet they all maintain the same carnival for Lesson Planning:

Some participants refused to grant consent for the observation of the lesson note books and some other documents.

Table 3: Individual Participants’ Data Related to use of Lesson Plan Book

Questions based on Category of Situation	Indicator	Observations
Weekly plan on English Language and Reading	6 participant	6 out of 7 participants do the Weekly programs on English but not regularly
Transpose lessons from curriculum and schemes of work	1participant (S3BE52AF)	All the teachers (except one), did not attempt transposing from curriculum to scheme of work, especially as most of them did not have a copy of the curriculum. One teacher (S1BA5A1)tried stating competences without the curriculum
Identify weekly learning outcome	2 out of 7 (S1BA5A1F & S3BE62A)F,	Only 2 teachers out of the 7 sometimes identifies learning outcome in the lessons
State teaching /learning strategies & didactic materials for each lesson	4 out of 7 (S1BA5A1F,S2BA5A2M, S2BA6A2F, S3BE6A2F)	Majority of the teachers (4/7) state the teaching/learning strategies. None of the teachers used didactic materials in teaching any lesson
Organize pupils to work copoperatively in group at given stages of lessons	None of the participants did except S3BE6BF	At no point of any of lesson plans did any of the teachers mentioned where pupils would be organized to work in groups.
Regularly plan lessons respect stages/framework for a Reading lesson	Yes (6/7) except for participant S3BE6A2M	All the teachers except S3BE6A2M plans lessons on English Language regularly, but with few Reading lessons that do not respect the stages.
States Clear, concise specific objectives	Yes. 7/7	Objectives of individual lessons are stated, But all teachers only very few Reading lessons prepared within six months
Evaluation tests the attainment of lesson	No	The different evaluations observed in individual lesson plans do not align with the stated objectives
Teach Reading process before the reading text	Not quite	When teaching Reading, most of the teachers concentrated on SWB and reading aloud. They hardly move from process to text.

- Have Lesson Note Book (6/8)
- Transpose from curriculum 1/7 (Directly from curriculum to classroom)
- Plan Lessons on EL (6/8)
- Teach Reading (very few lessons planned - SWB, Read Aloud and RC)
- State learning outcome
- State strategies and materials 4/8
- Organize pupils’ group work 1/8
- Regular individual plan 6/8 (very few Reading Lessons taught and stages of lesson not respected)
- Clear and concise specific objective 6/7
- Evaluate test lesson attainment (0/7 – no alignment between evaluation and objective)

➤ *Other Documents*

Table 4: Individual Participants’ Data Related to Use of other Institutional Classroom Documents

Document	Questions based on Category of Situations	Indicator	Observations
Record of Work Book	Recording daily, weekly & monthly activities regularly	Not regularly	Three teachers manage to fill the record book but not regularly. Four others do not fill at all. None of the three covers teaches Reading regularly, and none, was up to date with Reading program.
	Teaches Reading daily, weekly / monthly	No	
	Cover daily, weekly and monthly programs	No	
Class Timetable	Weekly program present on the timetable	Yes	All the teachers have the Weekly program present on their timetable but

	Time allocated for library	No	no time allocated for projects and other outdoors activities to improve reading. The timetables of the different teachers do not however match with the dates and contents in the pupils’ books and the teacher’s lesson plan book.
	Time allocated for project or other outdoors Reading/literacy activities	No	
	Timetable matches with scheme, lesson plan and pupils books	No	
English Course Books (Readers)	State prescribed copies of Readers	Yes	The Readers have the different qualities but their reading activities do not correspond with other language skills. All the teachers have The teacher also have the SWB book that accompanies the Reader
	Other text books meant for the pupils’ levels	Yes	
	Text set within the socio – cultural context of Cameroon	Yes	
	Text contents are interdisciplinary	Yes	
	Texts are accompanied by explicit and colourful pictures	Yes	
	Reading activities related to other language skills	Not quite	

Source: Teachers’ Individual Classroom Documents

Regarding the effective use of other class documents as part of the transposition process and permitting the understanding of teachers’ relationship to knowledge, data presented on the table above indicate that most of the teachers do not effectively put these documents to use for several individual reasons.

➤ *The Record of Work Book:*

- Four teachers (**S1BA6A1**, **S3BE5A2F**, **S3BE6A2M**, and **S3BE6B2F**) have but do not use the Record of Work
- Teacher **S3BE6A2M** does not have a Record of Work book at all.
- The rest of the teachers have incomplete records.
- Teacher **S1BA5A1F** fills the record correctly does not record work regularly.
- Teachers **S2BA5A2M** & **S2BA6A2F** record work in disorder and not regularly.

According to most of the teachers, recording work done does not make any sense to them. Most of the class 6 teachers say they are interested only in having the pupils get good results in the end of course exams.

- “Taking time to fill records is not necessary”
- “my objective to make the children pass have to be attained”,
- “I have to make good results rather than feeling documents. It is time consuming for nothing” (**S3BE6B2F**, **S3BE6A2M**, **S1BA6A1F**, **S3BE52AF**).
- I don’t fill the document regularly because it is complicated and difficult to understand.
- “... Many colleagues do not also know to use the books and are not even interested. So it is difficult to get help”.

The above verbatim reveal that teachers are not even knowledgeable about their responsibilities in organizing knowledge. Despite its important role in documenting taught knowledge so as to track teaching activities and pupils’ progress, the teachers consider recording work done as waste of time. The verbatim and findings contrast some related literature on teacher quality. A good teacher is identified as

that who should have good organizational competences, such as being able to organize and manage students’ learning and learning progressions, tackling professional duties and technical dilemmas, and managing their own professional development. Keeping record of work done by the learner permits the teacher to remember what the learner already knows as the constructivist who holds that the most important single factor influencing learning is what the learner already knows. The five petals representing the teacher’s relationship to knowledge and the source and resource of knowledge (shown in the literature) indicates the teacher’s role in organizing and planning knowledge. After teaching knowledge must be evaluated to permit future planning and to measure program coverage. Ignoring the record of work means that teachers do not plan and organize knowledge taught and learned, therefore, disrespecting the institutional norms. Not being able to plan from previous evaluation of work done and pupils’ progress, consequently results to poor learning outcome.

➤ *The Timetable*

- All teachers have all the teachers have timetables with weekly programs.
- Teachers do not respect the timetables and do not match dates and time in weekly plan
- No time allocated or outdoor Reading activities

The timetable data show that all the teachers have timetables with weekly programs. It was however noticed that the timetables have been there for purpose of inspection. Teachers were not respecting timetable. Dates and time indicated in the weekly plan and the children exercise books do not match. Most of the teachers say that they are the masters of the class and work according to the pupils’ pace, given that most of them are slow. To the teachers therefore timetables cannot be respected. It is also observed on all the timetable that time is not allocated for practical or outdoors Reading lessons.

Time management is a very important part of planning and classroom praxis which help in the enhancement of the internal didactic transposition process. Being part of the Basic

knowledge, English Language from which the Reading skill stems has a 60% of the overall study time at school. This means it has been allocated the highest number of hours to study Basic Knowledge with 138 hours a year and at least six (6) hours a week allocated for English Language. This means English Language is possibly taught for one hour fifteen minutes (1 hour 15 minutes) each day. In other words English Language should have a double periods or could be taught twice a day. Therefore, teachers are constrained to respect the teaching time allocated for English, exploring it for Reading which is a main skill in English. Not being able to manage the time as revealed in the data finding lead us to the interpretation that teachers' organizational knowledge is fragile. Thus a reason for pupils' poor Reading ability.

- *Didactic Materials*

It is observed from the tables that no didactic materials were pasted on the class wall to enhance Reading skills.

- *Course Books (Readers)*

All the teachers have the Readers and the Readers all have the expected qualities as shown on the tables above but for the fact that the context in the different units did not match the selected themes that aligns the National Competencies. It was observed that teachers could not align course book contents to with curriculum content to teach given lessons, that is why most of the teachers as revealed in the interview data were using only the course books to teach English and Reading without harmonizing with curriculum and scheme of work contents.

We realize that the teachers are not able to carry this task appropriately due to their insufficient institutional knowledge. This uncordial relationship to institutional knowledge negatively affect pupils' ability to develop necessary skills. In other words, this inability and lack of interest in didactically organizing Reading bodies of knowledge from the bases of internal didactic transposition in which teachers are constrained, leads to the thinking that pupils do not receive quality education, which is the top priority of the Cameroonian nation. Within the context of the present study, this uncordial relationship to institutional knowledge leads to slow development of Communication and Lifelong learning competences in general and the Reading competencies in particular. The quality of the teachers as guarantors of quality education therefore has to be questioned from the point of view of their institutional knowledge.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study examined how primary school teachers' institutional relationship to reading knowledge within the framework of Internal Didactic Transposition influences the development of learners' reading competencies. Empirical literature suggest teachers as mediators, responsible for transposing knowledge from organized bodies of institutional knowledge to classroom knowledge, giving their important role in Internal Didactic Transposition process (Chevallard, 1985; 1992; Lenoire et al, 2002; 2019; Artaud, 1995; Chevallard & Bosch, 2020; Stromskag & Chevallard, 2022; 2024; Ravel, 2003; Bosch, 2014; Katona, 2022). While

teachers are normatively pointed guarantors of quality education within the national and international context (Law N° 98/004, 1998; UNESCO, 2024, update), the evidence is false in the case of the Cameroon primary school teachers considered masters of all subjects in the primary curriculum (MINEUB, 2018/19; Moulakdi, & Bouchamma, 2020, Alemnge & Oben, 2024; Kuchah et al, 2024). This is evident in the English Language/Reading classroom where transposition from the curriculum to the classroom is flawed and learners Reading competences seriously hampered (Akah Mba, 2017).

Key findings in this study suggest that teachers' mediation between learners and institutional knowledge, often met neglect of crucial didactic documents such as the curriculum, the scheme, lesson plan books, the Record of Work books, the timetable and other didactic tools. This neglect suggests disconnection from institutional norms (Chevallard, 1985; 1989; 1992; Perrenaud, 1998, Ravel, 2003; Bosch & Garcon, 2006; Chevallard & Bosch, 2013; Stromskag & Chevallard, 2022; 2024; Ruetel et al, 2013). Many teachers find the curriculum confusing or unnecessary, leading them to rely on class readers and often neglecting proper lesson planning and regular teaching schedules. This results to improvise and uncoordinated teaching approach that negatively impacts pupils' reading abilities.

Classroom observations and interviews further supported these findings, showing that teachers do not consistently teach planned lessons or use necessary institutional documents. This confirms previous findings of related studies (Belibi, 2018; Nforbi & Siewoué, 2015; Akah Mba, 2017) which suggest that most ELT teachers teach students without actually having the syllabus, and more others teach without actually planning the lessons; thus, opposing the stipulated laws and declarations (LAW N° 98..., 1998, MINEDUB – CPSC, 2018/19; UNESCO, 2014; 2015; UNESCO, 2024; EFA, 2013/14; UNICEF, 2019; 2024) which qualify the teachers as guarantors of universal and national quality education. This substantial gap in teachers' relationship with institutional knowledge significantly affects their ability to develop reading competencies in pupils. Like Chevallard, Lenoire (2003) echoes the important role of the teacher in modifying or filtering knowledge the learners already have following stated goals of the curriculum which stands as the voice of the society. The Cameroon Primary school curriculum (MINEDUB, 2018/19) and other documents such as (UNESCO ICE, 1975, Vegnaud, 2001; ASCL, 2017,) emphasize the important role of the teacher in Lesson planning as well as the importance of lesson planning in achieving educational goals. If teachers spontaneously ignore these necessary institutional documents, then we assume that bodies of knowledge taught in general terms, and Reading bodies of knowledge in particular are not taken from appropriate instituted sources before getting to the classroom, causing a drift from knowledge to be taught to knowledge taught.

These findings highlight concerns about teacher quality and the need for better support and clearer guidelines to improve teachers' engagement with institutional knowledge. The implications for education are profound, particularly within the domain of didactics. This study not only advances our understanding of the internal didactic transposition of reading but also offers valuable insights for educational institutions, policy makers, and didactics researchers.

By addressing deficiencies in teachers' relationships with institutional knowledge, this research provides practical and theoretical insights that can help improve educational practices and outcomes.

A. Implications for Educational Stakeholders and Policy Makers

- *Systematic Educational Monitoring*

The research emphasizes the necessity of systematic educational monitoring. According to Cameroonian education law (Rep. of Cameroon, 1998), teachers are regarded as guarantors of quality education, responsible for teaching, assessing, and providing educational prowess. However, this study reveals that teachers often limit their responsibilities to teaching and assessing without thoroughly engaging with institutional knowledge. Therefore, it is crucial for policymakers to clearly define teachers' roles, especially regarding their relationship to knowledge.

- *Top-Down Monitoring*

The study uncovers a troubling disconnect between teachers and institutional norms. Many teachers neglect vital didactic documents like curricula and schemes of work, leading to an isolated and improvised approach to lesson planning and teaching. This neglect suggests a failure to implement educational and curricular goals, underscoring the need for ongoing, top-down monitoring of schools and teacher activities.

- *Continuous Professional Development and In-service Training*

Inconsistencies in the transposition process, stemming from teachers' misunderstandings of institutional documents, adversely affect pupils' reading abilities. Continuous professional development and in-service training are essential to enhance teachers' understanding of the didactic transposition process and its impact on student learning. Policymakers and educational stakeholders must ensure that teachers understand the importance of institutional constraints and conditions for effective teaching.

- *Raising Academic Standards of Teachers*

Additionally, the findings suggest that teachers struggle to harmonize content from various necessary documents, leading to improvised and inconsistent knowledge delivery. This issue highlights the need for improved quality in both pre-service and in-service teacher training programs. The study calls for raising academic standards for teacher recruitment and ensuring that professional growth is supported by quality development and monitoring.

➤ *Improved Educational Outcomes*

Overall, the study underscores the critical role of teachers' engagement with institutional knowledge in providing quality education and developing learners' reading competencies. It calls for enhanced support, clearer guidelines, and systematic monitoring to address the deficiencies identified and improve educational outcomes in Cameroon.

By addressing significant issues in teachers' institutional relationships with reading knowledge, this research highlights the need for improved teacher training, ongoing professional development, and systematic monitoring to ensure that educational goals are met. It provides valuable insights for educational institutions, policymakers, and stakeholders at various levels, aiming to enhance the quality of education and students' reading competences in Cameroon.

Implementing these recommendations aims to enhance practical applications of research outcomes and improve the quality of education and pupils' reading competences in Cameroon.

➤ *To Address the Gaps Identified, the Following Recommendations are Proposed:*

- **Professional Development and Monitoring:** Organize continuous in-service training and monitoring at the school level, facilitated by the Ministry of Basic Education. Expert teams should visit schools regularly to ensure proper use of institutional documents and understanding of didactic transposition.
- **Access to Institutional Documents:** Ensure all teachers have access to necessary institutional documents, such as curricula, and provide printed copies to each teacher.
- **Specialized Training:** Policy makers should train specialist teachers in basic subjects like Mathematics and English Language to address confusion and lack of mastery in subjects teachers did not specialize in during their education.
- **In-School Seminars and Follow-Up:** Conduct regular in-school seminars and follow-up sessions to address teachers' difficulties and emphasize the importance of quality didactic transposition

V. CONCLUSION

This study examined the critical role of teachers' relationships to institutional knowledge in developing learners' reading competences through the concept of internal didactic transposition. It found that effective transposition of knowledge from curriculum to classroom significantly enhances pupils' reading skills and contributes to quality education. Key insights highlighted that teachers' flawed understanding of their institutional responsibilities negatively impacts pupils' reading abilities. Many teachers neglect essential documents like the curriculum and schemes of work, leading to improvised lesson planning. Additionally, teachers' ignorance of current teaching approaches and methods shows disconnect from institutional norms. The lack of adherence to timetables and record-keeping further indicates their inability

to plan and organize knowledge effectively, contributing to pupils' poor reading performance. The research underscores the importance of comprehensive teacher training programs that address not only content knowledge but also institutional, pedagogical, and psychological aspects of teaching reading. Such a holistic approach can significantly enhance learners' reading competences and educational outcomes. The study's contributions provide new insights into the didactic transposition process and offer practical recommendations for improving teacher education programs. It suggests that targeted interventions in teacher education can lead to better literacy outcomes. Future research should explore long-term impacts and external factors such as parental involvement and home literacy environments. n

The research faced challenges, including managing diverse samples and collecting accurate self-reported data, but these were addressed through careful methodological design and rigorous data analysis. Ultimately, this study highlights the essential role of educators in shaping students' reading competences and calls for ongoing efforts to support and develop effective teaching practices. Educational stakeholders and policymakers must continue to prioritize and invest in teachers' professional development to foster a quality learning environment where all learners can achieve their full potential.

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